

Graphical user interface and technology requirements

Operating screens with a minimum of text provide users with options for data entry or selection of default values before they are prompted to run optimization routines. A tutorial and background information on the principles of SSNM are provided in the Help function. The software has a built-in database for storing information such as default values (e.g., fertilizer sources, nutrient concentrations, prices, etc.) and developed fertilizer strategies. The NuDSS also provides the option for printing user-customized reports.

NuDSS 1.0 was programmed using Visual Basic 6.0 and MS Access. The accompanying database software FarmMonitor 1.0 was developed using Delphi 5.0 and MS Access. Both applications run under MS Windows 95/98/NT or Windows 2000 on a personal computer with at least 16-Mb RAM, a 66-mHz processor, a 100-Mb hard disk, and a CD-ROM. The NuDSS and FarmMonitor will be officially released by the end of 2001.

References

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PRICE: a decision support tool for the control of weeds in tropical irrigated rice

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Herbicide use is increasing in Asian rice production and is likely to continue in the near future. Direct seeding is also increasingly replacing transplanting as the dominant cropping system. There is a direct interaction between the availability of rice herbicides and the increase in use of direct-seeding technology. Direct seeding is viable in high-productivity irrigated systems if cost-effective herbicides are included in the control of weeds (Naylor 1996).

The past decade has seen a slow migration of labor from rural communities to the industrializing urban areas in Bangladesh, following a general trend across Asia. This has led to increasing labor costs, which have made direct seeding with the use of herbicides much more viable. Herbicide use is also favorable in transplanted rice. Research has shown a benefit-cost ratio of 16:1 (up to 25:1 with complete control) for the use of herbicides versus 3.3:1 for hand weeding (Naylor 1996). In Bangladesh, labor costs are as much as 44% of the variable costs of production (IRRI 1995). Herbicide use reduces costs in both direct-seeded and transplanted rice by reducing the cost of

labor for hand weeding. The use of direct seeding reduces labor costs further by eliminating the need for labor to maintain nurseries and transplant.

The major concern is how best to govern and regulate the use of rice herbicides as their use becomes more widespread. To do this, it is necessary to understand the effects of use on the population of the area, the effects of use on the environment, and the economic implications of usage or nonusage of herbicides.

Decision support systems and risk associated with increased herbicide use

The increased use of herbicides carries with it new risks. Herbicides may cause acute poisoning of workers or nontarget organisms. Residues may persist in soil and water, causing chronic health effects on both the ecosystem and humans. Rice plant vigor may be damaged if soil residues persist at phytotoxic levels until the next crop is established.

Decision support systems (DSS) provide a framework within which the severity of these risks can be evaluated along with the postulated yield and income benefits from herbicide use.

PRICE (Pesticide Residues in Irrigated Cereal Ecosystems) is a DSS that is partly data-driven and partly model-driven. It was developed to help determine environmentally acceptable and relevant herbicides for use in irrigated rice in the high-potential Indo-Gangetic plains of northern India and Bangladesh, but it is also useful in other tropical regions where irrigated rice is grown

(Laister et al 2000). Data on rice herbicides relevant to the buildup of residues in the environment and their effect on nontarget organisms, particularly fish, which are often grown in conjunction with rice, were collated and reviewed.

Target audience and environment

PRICE should prove useful to policy-makers and extension workers, including those in NGOs, to help give advice to farmers, and to farmers themselves. Registration authorities may also use it to quickly identify problem compounds. PRICE may help research institutes and entities (governmental, university, and commercial) to define research priorities for study in terms of aspects of pesticide fate in the field environment.

The PRICE database contains information necessary to run a model of the environmental fate of herbicide residues. The model predicts the fate of the applied herbicide in the field environment. It takes into account the soil type, weather conditions, and crop (direct-seeded or transplanted) calendar. Also available are scenarios based on geographic information systems and environmental conditions of rice-growing locations in Bangladesh.

Content

A full list of all rice herbicides available is contained within the database, which gives limited information, such as manufacturer, product name, and use. Chemicals that are registered for use in the Indo-Gangetic floodplain contain more detailed information. This part of the database contains information on physico-chemical properties, structure, mammalian toxicology, ecotoxicology, environmental fate, metabolic pathways, and species controlled. The information is accessed by clicking through a series of screens for a particular compound or by

browsing through the complete list of compounds for a particular attribute.

The information within the database has been compiled from several sources: Tomlin (1994), Roberts (1998), Aizawa (1982), Johnson (1987), and Herner (1989).

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Data entry has been designed to be simple (in general, options must be chosen from pull-down selection boxes). The predicted environmental concentrations are compared with known data on acute and chronic effects of the compound on target species. A risk level (low, medium, or high) is given for the soil, surface water, and groundwater using a system of easily identifiable icons. Separately, economic costs and benefits are calculated based on the cost of applying the compound, the expected level of control, and the expected yield increase.

The database part of PRICE was developed using Microsoft Access 97™. The model part was developed in Microsoft Excel 97™. Access is not required to run the DSS, but Excel is required. The DSS is available on a CD-ROM from the Crop Protection Programme, Natural Resources International Ltd., Pembroke, Chatham Maritime, Kent ME4 4NN, UK (tel: + 44 1634 883630, fax: + 44 1634 883937, e-mail Andy Ward at a.ward@gre.ac.uk). Further information is available from the author (richard.wilkins@ncl.ac.uk). A simple installation procedure loads the DSS onto the hard disk (occupying about 20 Mb). A Pentium or more powerful processor running Windows 95 or a later operating system is required.

The development of PRICE is still under way and the current version is not "bug-free." In particular, the look and feel

of the interface need evaluation by potential users and the model part requires verification (requiring analysis of soil and water concentrations of pesticides under experimental conditions). PRICE was developed for herbicides on the Indo-Gangetic Plain, but there is no reason why the model could not be used in other rice-growing areas and expanded for use with all pesticides. Such development requires access to appropriate data on soils and climate and on additional pesticides. Development depends on further funding being obtained.

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